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Aire expression dysregulation in ALS.

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Tolerance of self and associated alterations in homeostatic immune regulation may be a recurrent theme in autoimmune disease pathology. AIRE trains developing lymphocytes through negative selection of self-peptides (also known as tissue-restricted antigen, or TRA) on the thymus. AIRE may function in the periphery, as well, to establish and maintain tolerance of self. We used transcriptome technologies to study key component gene expression in the neurodegenerative disease amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and describe here the discovery of altered AIRE expression in primary tissues of humans with ALS and in iPS induced pluripotent stem cell models of the neurodegenerative disease.